

Towards Contract Based Assertions in IEC 61499 Applications

Duc Do Tran, Jörg Walter, Kim Grüttner, Frank Oppenheimer
OFFIS – Institute for Information Technology, Oldenburg, Germany
Email: {duc.do.tran, joerg.walter, kim.gruettner, frank.oppenheimer}@offis.de

Abstract—The IEC 61499 standard addresses the topic of function blocks for industrial process measurement and control systems. It defines a generic model for distributed control systems and offers more flexibility but requires severe discipline from the designer, since arbitrary event driven execution models can be difficult to analyze and debug. Presuming a composable function block model, contracts allow formally specifying assumptions and guarantees on the ports of a function block. This work proposes an initial concept for integrating behavioral assumptions and guarantees into function blocks in IEC 61499. Monitors implementing these contracts can observe the function block’s behavior during its execution. They check the adherence to the contract either on a local node or after distributing the function blocks on a network of controllers. In this work, we have implemented our concept based on 4diac, an open-source IEC 61499 compatible framework. We illustrate and evaluate our concept with a simple water level control system.

Keywords—IEC 61499, Contract-based design, Distributed Control System, Monitoring, Safety

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we describe an approach to augment IEC 61499 compliant control system models with behavioral contracts. With such contracts, we enable the attachment of a formal behavioral specification to functions blocks that describe the behavior of industrial control systems. This work proposes an initial concept for integrating behavioral contracts as assumptions and guarantees into IEC 61499 function block diagrams. Through the it’s formulation as standard compliant assumption and guarantee function blocks it is possible to integrate our proposed scheme into existing IEC 61499 modeling and run-time environments.

After resource allocation and function block mapping our introduced assumption and guarantee function blocks server as assertions that observe the function block’s behavior during execution. They check the adherence to the contract either on a local node or, after distributing the function blocks, on a network of controllers. In this work we have implemented our concept based on 4diac framework. We illustrate and evaluate our concept with a simple water level control system.

The paper is structured as follows. In the following section we describe briefly the state of the art. In Section III we explain the necessary background. This section in particular gives the reader a brief overview on the IEC 61499 standard and basic principles of contract-based design. In Section IV we describe our approach of integrating Assume and Guarantee Function Blocks in Function Block diagrams and in Section V we introduce an illustrative use case example and shows how these concepts can be integrated into the 4diac framework. Here we evaluate the example based on the 4diac run-time

system. The final section gives a conclusion and an outlook on future work.

II. STATE OF THE ART

A contract-based methodology for the design of controllers was introduced in [1]. This work proposes a platform-based design approach, which applies contracts between components to deal with integration issues for different aspects of a design. [2], [3] introduce a methodology for combining a platform-based design methodology and assume-guarantee (A/G) contracts to integrate heterogeneous modeling and analysis frameworks for control system synthesis as well as optimization and verification. This approach was demonstrated on the design of embedded controllers for aircraft electric power distribution. An approach for consistent integration of nominal behavior function and the safety architecture of embedded systems in various industry domains by using contracts is introduced in [4]. Several research works have proposed a contract-based approach to the verification of IEC 61499 models. An approach using IEC 61499 for building hierarchical control systems in a master-slave arrangement, has been introduced by [5]. In this work, the interaction between components on different hierarchy levels has been verified by behavioral event contracts. In this sense, assumptions must cover the order of received input events. For output guarantees, the order of emitted events has to be ensured, if the received input event sequence fulfills the assumption. However, the contract specification in this work is limited to event sequences, acceptable for the function blocks and do not deal with the transfer of data through data ports. This leads to a verification algorithm considering only event sequences as defined in ECCs without any check for condition values of data variables. The work presented in [6] targets static verification at the component, algorithm and ECC levels of IEC 61499 function blocks. In this approach, the behavior of function blocks is manually translated into WhyML and enriched with the necessary contracts, consisting of pre- and post-conditions. This work demonstrated the correctness of component compositions, functional and transitional behavior on a set of use-cases in WhyML. Furthermore, [6] showed unsolved issues including automatic contract generation from function blocks and the establishment of defined semantics for reasoning on causal and timing properties on IEC 61499 models.

The idea of this work is to integrate Assume/Guarantee (A/G) Contracts into the IEC 61499 applications as assertions that check the correctness of the functional behavior at run-time. The contracts are modeled as additional Function Blocks (FB) in the model that check the input data of a behavior function block before the FB is triggered (Assumptions) and the output data of the FB (Guarantee).

III. BACKGROUND

A. IEC 61499 Standard

The IEC 61499 standard provides a graphical and textual description language for the specification of the structure and behavior of distributed application based on function block networks. IEC 61499 extends IEC 61131-1 by improving the encapsulation of software components to meet requirements of modern technology such as modularity, reusability, reconfiguration, portability, interoperability, flexibility, adaptability and extendibility.

Figure 1. Interface and ECC of Function Block

In the following sections, we will briefly introduce the different kinds of IEC 61499 function blocks and the application & device model. More information about IEC 61499 can be found in [8].

1) *Function block kinds*: IEC 61499 function blocks (FBs, see Fig. 1) exist in three different kinds: Basic Function Blocks (BFB), Composite Function Blocks (CFB) and Service Interface Function Blocks (SIFB). These function block types all have the same kind of interface (see Fig. 1(a)), which is represented by input events, output events, input data variables, and output data variables. Each data input/output must be associated with at least one input/output event respectively. However, input and output events do not need to be associated with input data and output data.

a) *Basic Function Blocks*: provide a tool to define operation and behavior of an FB using so-called Execution Control Charts (ECC), which is defined as a directed graph linking execution control states by execution control transitions (see Fig. 1(b)).

b) *Composite Function Blocks*: provide the ability to encapsulate a network of internal FBs. The behavior of a CFB relies on the behavior of its encapsulated function block network. A CFB can contain CFBs, BFBs and SIFBs.

c) *Service Interface Function Blocks*: provide the ability to communicate data values and events between hardware resources, including the capability to access specific parts of the hardware (e.g. direct I/O driver access). Unlike BFBs, the behavior of a SIFB must be implemented in a native programming language, e.g. C or C++.

2) *Application and device model of IEC 61499*: An IEC 61499 application is generated by connecting events and data variables of various FBs in a network. IEC 61499 also provides a device model to distribute the execution of FBs across multiple devices. Applications can execute on a single device or on a number of devices. On the other side, a device can run multiple applications or parts of applications at the same time or even just a part of a single application.

B. Assume/Guarantee Contract Theory

The Design-by-Contract approach was introduced by Bertrand Meyer for software specification via pre- and post-conditions of functions in Object-Oriented programming [9]. A contract is defined as a pair $\mathcal{C}(A, G)$ of $\langle \text{Assumptions}, \text{Guarantees} \rangle$ on the ports of a component and is called Assume-Guarantee Contract [10]. For example, an assumption A ensures that data on a specific input port of a component will never exceed a limited value. If this assumption is fulfilled, the guarantee G (has to be fulfilled) ensuring that data on a specific output of the component will not exceed a specified value. Formally this is an implication $A \rightarrow G$. Contracts provide abilities to cope with the complexity of systems through decomposition. They ease the integration across multiple domains and different functional component implementations from various suppliers, developed by different teams.

Contracts play an important role to support the specification, design and verification of large systems. Contract-based design relies on a hierarchical structure, where a system is decomposed into various subsystems. The application of contracts in a hierarchical structure can be performed by horizontal and vertical contracts. A horizontal contract deals with components at the same level of abstraction and is supported by contract composition and conjunction operators. A vertical contract is supported by refinement operators in order to express a contract refinement relationship with respect to another level of abstraction. In the context of IEC 61499 FBs, horizontal contracts can be applied to the composition of BFBs, SIFBs and CFBs. Vertical contracts can be applied from one CFB level to another.

IV. INTEGRATING BEHAVIORAL CONTRACTS INTO 4DIAC

We selected 4diac as development environment for the example application. 4diac IDE [7] is based on the Eclipse open tool framework. It provides an extensible engineering environment for the development of IEC 61499 applications. The IEC 61499 compliant run-time environment FORTE is implemented in C++. The process of this work is implemented as follows: 1) *Modeling the behavior and contract function blocks*; 2) *Modeling the control system application*; 3) *Deploying with FORTE for test and evaluation*.

A. Development of basic function blocks

1) *Behavior function blocks*: An assumed template for a function block for a simplified behavior modeling of each component in our IEC 61499 Application is shown in Fig. 5. The interface of our template FB has input events *Active*, *Request*, and *Stop*; output events are *Ready* and *Response*. The behavior of each template FB is specified by an ECC, as shown in Fig. 2. All behavior FBs in our example application (see Fig. 5) use this function block template. Only the algorithm *Math_Model* is different in each of the instantiated FBs.

Figure 2. Execution Control Chart (ECC) of behavior function block

2) *Contract function blocks*: We created FBs for generic specification of common contracts such as Number-Comparison-Contract or Range-Comparison-Contract. In the following paragraphs, we introduce our generic contract FBs:

a) *Number-Comparison-Contract*: (shown in Fig. 5) This FB performs a comparison on real numbers between the input number (*InputNum*) and the comparison value (*CompValue*). Input *CompType* specifies the type of comparison: 'GT': [$>$]; 'GE': [\geq]; 'LT': [$<$]; 'LE': [\leq]; 'EQ': [$=$]; 'NEQ': [\neq]. The *Response* event is triggered when the comparison is true (i.e. satisfaction of contract). This event sets data output $QO = True$ in order to enable operations linked to the next FB. The *Error* event is triggered if either the result of the comparison is incorrect (i.e. a violation of contract) or the FB has invalid input values. This event sets $QO = False$ to disable operations linked to the next FB. The data port *Infos* is associated with events *Response* and *Error* and represents additional status information. The input data port *QI* signals if all predecessor components succeeded. Only if *QI* is true the FB is activated.

b) *Range-Comparison-Contract*: (shown in Fig. 5) This FB checks whether $InputNum(i)$ is within the range of $SmallerNum(s)$ and $GreaterNum(g)$. Most inputs and outputs (*Active*, *Request*, *Ready*, *Response*, *Error*, *QI*, *QO*, *Infos*) operate the same as in Number-Comparison-Contract. The comparison type *CompType* specifies comparison details: 'RCE': [$s \leq i \leq g$]; 'RCT': [$s < i < g$]; 'GEL': [$s \leq i < g$]; 'GLE': [$s < i \leq g$]; 'NRCE': [$(i < s) \cup (i > g)$]; 'NRCT': [$(i \leq s) \cup (i \geq g)$]; 'NGEL': [$(i < s) \cup (i \geq g)$]; 'NGLE': [$(i \leq s) \cup (i > g)$].

B. Modeling of the application system

Fig. 3 illustrates the principle of modeling the control system using a A/G contract. The assumption function block (AFB) checks contract satisfaction for input data *in* of behavior function block (BeFB), e.g. comparison between input data *in* and comparison number *cn*. In case the assumption is satisfied, the *rsp* event of AFB is triggered and activates the *req* event of BeFB for normal execution. Simultaneously, $QO = True$ of AFB enables the guarantee function block (GFB) later on. Otherwise the assumption was violated, which is undefined in pure contract theory. We chose to emit output event *Error* in this case. If the assumption is not fulfilled, the *err* is triggered and $QO = False$. It is linked to *req* of GFB, and due to $QI = False$, this subsequently triggers the *err* event of GFB.

After completion of BeFB, its result is available at *out* associated with event *rsp*. This event will activate the *req* event of GFB. If the *out* satisfies the guarantee, the *rsp* event of GFB is triggered and $QO = True$. Otherwise, *err* is triggered and $QO = False$. *err* is connected to the *stp* event of BeFB to stop its operation in case of errors. Finally, QO , *err*, and *req* of GFB connect to *QI* and *req* of the next AFB to continue contract monitoring for the next component.

Figure 3. Basic principle of contracts in IEC 61499

V. EVALUATION

The main idea of this work is to demonstrate the feasibility of applying contracts by using FBs for safety monitoring. We analyze and evaluate the implementation of the water tank example [11] as shown in Fig. 5.

A cylindrical water container is equipped with an inlet pipe at the top, and an outlet pipe at the bottom. The container has a diameter $D = 5m$ and a height $H = 9m$. The inlet and outlet cross sections are $S_{in} = 0.5m^2$ and $S_{out} = 0.16m^2$ respectively. The requirement for the controller design is that "after 10 seconds since start-up the system must guarantee a continuous outlet flow F_{out} in the range of $[1.0 \ 2.0] m^3/s$ and the system must never overflow". This requirement must be fulfilled under the assumptions that "the inlet pressure is a constant value of $P \geq 190KPa$, the water density is $\rho = 1000kg/m^3$ and the evaporation rate is $\epsilon = 0.25m^3/h$ ". The water tank control system is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Block diagram and methodology for the tank control system

The implementation is based on the principle explained in Section IV-B. For evaluation, we create a testbed with a water source (WSFB) and a request generator (RGFB). WSFB provides values for *Pressure* after the *Active* event is triggered. RGFB triggers *EO* events dependent on the value of *SampleTime*.

When deploying the system to the FORTE run-time, we set a constant pressure value of $735 kPa$, thus the AFB of the valve is fulfilled. The valve aperture is always in the range $[0 \ 1]$, which means that the maximum value of the inlet flow of the tank is $9.585 m^3/s$. Therefore, the guarantee of the valve and the assumption of the tank are satisfied. The controller adjusts the valve position to meet the requirement of the desired water levels configured with *Accuracy* and *WaterLevelMax*. In

Figure 5. Building of an application system (water tank example) with contract

this case, we set $Accuracy = 0.9$ and $WaterLevelMax = 8$. This means the controller provides command values to get measured water level ($MeasureWL$) stable at 7.2m.

For the first test, the error value of the sensor is 0 ($ErrorRate = 0$). The measured outlet flow ($FlowOut$) and measured level ($WaterLevel$) of the tank yields stable values of 1.9016 and 7.1997, respectively. The valve position is held at 0.1984, which leads to the inlet flow of the tank ($FlowIn$) being a stable value of 1.9019. Thus the entire system is stable and meets all requirements.

In the next test we change $ErrorRate$ to 0.05 and the measured water level at the controller varies between $7.2m \cdot (1 \pm 0.05)$, but the contracts are not violated and the system operates normally. To continue the testing, we assume that system experiences a congestion at the outlet flow, leading to an outlet cross-section less than the expected value (e.g. $S_{Outlet} = 0.06$). We also assume the water level at this time is $WaterLevel = 6.8693$. This leads to $FlowOut = 0.6966$, which violates the tank's guarantees. The GFB of the tank triggers an *Error* event immediately, subsequently stopping all components.

We performed further tests with various cases of hidden contract violation, for example a sensor error rate greater than the expected value ($ErrorRate = 0.1$), or a broken outlet ($S_{Outlet} = 0.36$). For all these hypothetical cases, the system always detected the error condition through the monitors.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this work, we have motivated and introduced contracts for IEC 61499 function blocks. These contracts have been expressed as assumption and guarantee function blocks that encapsulate the behavior function block, thus acting as pre- and post conditions for the execution of the behavior. The contract implementation as IEC 61499 FBs allows a seamless integration with the standard IEC 61499 deployment process and allows online monitoring of IEC 61499 applications.

The presented work is a first step towards IEC 61499 function block contracts. The current implementation has several limitations, which should be fixed in future work:

- Support for a property specification language to express generic behavioral and temporal properties.
- Automatic checking of horizontal contract composition and vertical contract refinement.

- Tool support for the generation of function block interface traces to visualize contract violation.
- Support for automatic function block communication refinement and code generation for distributed monitors.

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